

ferent between japonica and indica waxy rice starches, whereas the pasting temperature, final at 95°C, cooled to 50°C, and consistency were not significant. The results showed the differ-

ences between breakdown and setback amylograph viscosities because indica has higher value of peak viscosity than japonica waxy rice starch. ■

Physicochemical properties of japonica and indica waxy rice. Korea, 1996.

Characteristic	Waxy rice		LSD ^c
	Japonica ^a	Indica ^b	
	<i>Milled waxy rice</i>		
Chemical property			
Amylose (%)	2.0	2.6	*
Alkali spreading value (1-7)			
1.7% KOH	6.3	6.5	ns
1.4% KOH	3.8	3.8	ns
Protein (%)	7.5	7.6	ns
Mg (ppm)	887	893	ns
K (ppm)	2,239	2,676	**
Mg/K	1.28	1.09	**
Texturogram			
Hardness (kg)	9.83	6.95	*
Adhesiveness	-1.18	-1.20	ns
Cohesiveness	0.17	0.19	ns
Springiness	0.96	0.93	ns
Gumminess	1.47	1.24	ns
Chewiness	1.40	1.19	ns
	<i>Waxy rice starch</i>		
Water-binding capacity (%)	196	183	**
Gel consistency (mm)	78(S) ^d	88(S)	ns
Transmittance (% at 625 nm)			
<70 °C	23.9-32.4	28.9-42.7	**
≤70 °C	76.3-78.4	78.2-78.8	ns
Swelling power			
<70 °C	1.4-7.7	1.33-5.1	*
≤70 °C	over 20	over 20	ns
Amylography (RVU)			
Pasting temperature (°C)	70.2	70.6	ns
Peak	273	281	*
Final at 95 °C	99	98	ns
Cooled 50 °C	135	132	ns
Breakdown	173	183	*
Setback	-138	-149	**
Consistency	35	34	ns

^aJaponica = Sinseonchalbyeo, Buklukbanna, Wonsanchalbyeo, Iri309, and Hwaseonchalbyeo. ^bIndica = Hankangchalbyeo, Iri352, IR29, IR65, and RD6. ^c*,** = significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level, respectively. ns = not significant. ^dBased on Cagampang et al (1973) = S:soft (61-100 mm).

A method of producing Basmati rice aroma from *Bassia* flowers

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The aroma of Basmati rice was identified as 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline (AP) by Buttery and colleagues, and Schieberle developed a simple method of its synthesis from proline and sugar. Our

group slightly modified this method. We reported (IRRN 17(5):9,1992) that the sweet smell of some indigenous varieties of unboiled fragrant rice was the same as that of our synthetic product, and this product, although proline-based, was different from AP. Using gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (GCMS) analysis, we tested pure AP from Schieberle's laboratory and have now established that the

fragrance of unboiled rice is the same as that of AP. We have also traced AP in the fresh flowers of *Bassia latifolia* in relatively large amounts. Because synthesis (by both Schieberle and us) is based on the Maillard reaction, it yields only microgram quantities of AP from grams of proline and sugar. For larger quantities, production of AP from *Bassia* was considered.

Paper chromatographic studies first established the *Bassia* fragrance as that of AP. We further confirmed this result using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; C18 microbondapak column, isocratic runs with methanol: water at 50:50, pump pressure 0.5 ml min⁻¹). Since we have found that AP-citrate remains stable for at least 6 mo, fresh flowers were macerated in excess citric acid, chromatographically purified, and compared with GCMS-tested standard AP, which was likewise treated with excess citric acid. Peaks for citric acid and AP-citrate were clearly visible in the standard and *Bassia* extracts. This observation may be the first one documenting the occurrence of AP in a flower. Steam distillation of *Bassia* flower and collection in pure citric acid thus yields AP-citrate that might be utilized after purification. ■

Effect of degree of polish on physical and gravimetric properties of rough rice

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Knowledge of rice's physical and gravimetric properties, such as grain size, bulk density, and porosity are important for designing systems for handling, transport, storage, drying, and other processes. Degree of polish is a most important parameter for trade purposes because milled rice quality, amount of bran, and oil content depend on it. This study determined the pro-